

EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF NEUROLOGICAL DISEASES AMONG THE POPULATION

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Abstract. To date, neurological diseases are a general medical problem that has profound socio-medical and economic consequences associated with their widespread prevalence among the population, disability, mortality due to the development of the terminal stage of the disease. Based on the interpretation of the data obtained, a methodological approach was used by a number of researchers who used it to evaluate various factors. Numerous clinical and epidemiological studies conducted in the world in recent years show that the prevalence of kidney disease is high and is not inferior to the prevalence of such socially significant diseases as diabetes mellitus, hypertension, heart failure.

Keywords: neurological diseases, early diagnosis, medical examination, hemodialysis.

РАННЯЯ ДИАГНОСТИКА НЕВРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ СРЕДИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ

Аннотация. На сегодняшний день неврологические заболевания представляют собой общемедицинскую проблему, имеющую глубокие социально-медицинские и экономические последствия, связанные с их широкой распространенностью среди населения, инвалидизацией, смертностью вследствие развития терминальной стадии заболевания. На основе интерпретации полученных данных ряд исследователей использовали методологический подход, применявший его для оценки различных факторов. Многочисленные клинико-эпидемиологические исследования, проведенные в мире за последние годы, показывают, что распространенность болезней почек высока и не уступает распространенности таких социально значимых заболеваний, как сахарный диабет, артериальная гипертензия, сердечная недостаточность.

Ключевые слова: неврологические заболевания, ранняя диагностика, диспансеризация, гемодиализ.

INTRODUCTION

Kidneys are one of the most important organs in the human body, as they provide normalization of pressure, removal of toxins and toxins, as well as control of blood elements. Kidney diseases often begin without pronounced symptoms and are diagnosed too late when the kidneys are irretrievably affected, so once a year we recommend doing laboratory tests of the kidneys to detect possible diseases at an early stage, stop or slow down the progression of kidney damage in time. The presence of chronic foci of infection, hyperlipidemia, arterial hypertension, drug abuse and other body processes lead to kidney pathologies. More common in people permanently residing in rural areas, the main risk factors for development and progression have been identified, and the relationship between the development of renal pathologies and overweight and obesity has been proven.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The most important preventive measures are to optimize the tactics of early detection and ways to prevent the progression of kidney diseases. We also found that the main tool for optimizing the tactics of early detection is screening, which is the most modern method of identifying risk factors and their effects on the development of CKD, which allows optimizing the process of early detection among the population, especially among rural residents. Screening made it possible to identify patients by 28.7% more than the initial appeal of the population to the primary health care unit.

RESULTS

Stages of prevention of development and progression of kidney diseases:

- creation of an electronic register of rural population included in development groups during screening studies;
- creation of a school for nephrological patients with a specific training program for groups of rural population who have a high risk of developing and progressing kidney pathology, who have been diagnosed.

DISCUSSION

In recent years, efforts have been made in the country to improve the quality of the system of providing medical care to persons suffering from nephrological diseases. Hemodialysis units are functioning in a number of republican and all regional medical institutions, providing a significant increase in the duration and quality of life of patients. At the same time, the analysis of the state of affairs showed the presence of a number of urgent problems that prevent the provision of full-fledged medical care to patients in need of hemodialysis care. In particular:

- first, the total number of places in medical institutions for hemodialysis is several times lower than the actual need, more than half of the hemodialysis units are located in unsuitable premises, and most hemodialysis machines have exceeded the established service life;
- secondly, there is a need to create a specialized medical center with regional units to provide highly qualified nephrological and hemodialysis care to the population, as well as kidney transplantation;
- third, uniform standards and protocols for the treatment of patients with terminal and acute renal insufficiency have not been implemented, as well as an effective system of early prevention, timely diagnosis of nephrological diseases, as well as procedures for selecting and referring patients for hemodialysis has not been established;
- fourth, there is an acute shortage of nephrologists and hemodialysis specialists due to the lack of a unified training program for nephrologists, hemodialysis doctors and other medical personnel of hemodialysis units;
- fifth, the opportunities of public-private partnership are not being used in creating a modern medical infrastructure for the treatment of nephrological diseases and solving the problems that have accumulated in this area;
- sixth, there are complex and opaque procedures for registration, certification and obtaining permits for the import and purchase of hemodialysis medical equipment and consumables, which restricts market access and competition between their manufacturers.

CONCLUSIONS

Timely diagnosis is the medical examination of the population and a thorough diagnosis and analysis of the laboratory data of the population and in the future to put them on record. In order to accelerate the solution of existing problems and shortcomings, as well as to ensure the development of modern infrastructure and qualitative improvement of the system of medical care for persons suffering from nephrological diseases: organization of systematic medical examinations of the population in primary health care institutions with the participation of leading specialists of republican specialized scientific and practical medical centers, clinics of higher medical educational institutions, republican multidisciplinary hospitals; improving the quality of specialized, high-tech nephrological medical care to the population at the regional and district levels of the healthcare system by introducing modern and effective methods of prevention, diagnosis and treatment; reduction of morbidity and mortality from nephrological diseases by creating an integrated system for organizing work on early prevention, timely detection, treatment and rehabilitation of patients with renal pathology at all levels of the health system, as well as reviewing and optimizing the process of diagnosis, selection and referral of patients for hemodialysis in accordance with international practice; ensuring an increase in the duration and quality of life of patients in need of hemodialysis care through the widespread use of high-tech methods and modern treatment standards; the introduction of unified modern standards and protocols for the diagnosis and treatment of renal diseases in adults and children at all stages of medical care, including the development and approval of mandatory clinical protocols for hemodialysis sessions; strengthening the material and technical base of nephrological and hemodialysis institutions by fully equipping them with modern high-tech diagnostic and therapeutic medical equipment, uninterrupted provision of spare parts for them, consumables for hemodialysis and related construction and repair work; creation of an effective system of training, retraining and advanced training of personnel for early prevention, timely detection and treatment of nephrological diseases; accelerated development of the private sector and public-private partnership in the provision of nephrological and hemodialysis care to the population.

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